

HYBRID GROUND–AERIAL FOREST INVENTORY USING QUADRUPED LIDAR DBH GROUND TRUTH FOR ALLOMETRIC CALIBRATION OF DRONE-BASED CROWN MEASUREMENTS

Theocharis Tsenis¹, Vasileios Barmpagiannos, Evangelos D. Spyrou¹, Vassilios Kappatos¹

¹Hellenic Institute of Transport, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, 6th Km Charilaou-Thermi Road, 57001, Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract: Accurate estimation of Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) remains a key limitation of drone-based forest inventories due to canopy occlusion and the site-specific bias of allometric models. This study presents a hybrid ground–aerial framework that integrates a quadruped robotic platform with unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) surveys to generate spatially aligned, high-accuracy DBH ground truth for model calibration. The quadruped is equipped with LiDAR, RGB imaging, and GNSS–IMU sensors, enabling direct trunk-level DBH measurements under dense forest canopy through adaptive navigation and multi-view data acquisition. Tree trunks are detected using an ensemble of deep learning models and fused with LiDAR point clouds to estimate DBH via robust geometric fitting. In parallel, UAV imagery is used to detect tree crowns and estimate crown dimensions across large forest areas. Spatial alignment of terrestrial and aerial observations enables local calibration of crown-based DBH estimation models. The proposed approach reduces estimation bias and improves inventory accuracy, supporting reliable biomass assessment, carbon accounting, and data-driven forest management.

Keywords: Quadruped robot, Forest ecosystem, Diameter at breast height; LiDAR sensing, Drone-based mapping, Allometric calibration

1. Introduction

Forests play a vital role in both environmental sustainability and the global economy, providing essential ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and the supply of timber and other renewable resources [1]. To effectively preserve these functions, continuous monitoring of forest structure and ecosystem health is required to support both short-term management actions and long-term ecological resilience [2]. However, conventional forest inventory practices face significant logistical constraints, relying heavily on labor-intensive and time-consuming field measurements that are difficult to scale across large or inaccessible areas [3]. Recent advances in quadruped robotic platforms equipped with sophisticated sensing payloads address many of these limitations by enabling reliable traversal of rugged terrain and dense, mature forest canopies. This ground-level perspective provides a horizontal sensing viewpoint that is often unattainable using aerial or satellite-based platforms [4, 5]. Such terrestrial mobility is particularly critical for accurately capturing fundamental biophysical variables, including Diameter at Breast Height (DBH), which remains a primary indicator of forest condition, biomass estimation, and growth dynamics [3].

Traditional manual DBH measurement techniques, typically based on calipers or diameter tapes, are inherently laborious and become impractical in dense stands or topographically complex environments [6]. Moreover, these approaches are unsuitable for high-frequency data collection, limiting their applicability for near real-time forest monitoring. While remote sensing methods—such as drone-based canopy scanning—offer scalable coverage, they commonly rely on allometric relationships to infer DBH from crown characteristics [7]. The accuracy of such models is strongly dependent on frequent calibration using high-quality ground-truth data, as allometric parameters vary with species composition and environmental conditions, including local topography, slope, and solar exposure [8, 9]. When these models are applied without periodic, site-specific recalibration, significant bias can be introduced into aggregated forest metrics, ultimately degrading the reliability of biomass and carbon stock assessments [10].

Current forest monitoring practices remain heavily reliant on manual measurements, a methodology that this work seeks to modernize through autonomous systems. Traditionally, DBH is recorded 1.3 meters above ground using instruments such as diameter tapes or calipers. Standard protocol requires foresters to wrap the tape around the trunk at breast height, ensuring it remains level and perpendicular to the tree axis. In sloped terrain, measurements are taken from the uphill side or at a calculated midpoint to account for elevation differences. Multi-stemmed trees are handled individually, with each stem measured separately if divergence occurs below the standard height.

While manual methods provide high accuracy for individual trees, they are labor-intensive, require physical access to every specimen, and pose safety risks in dense or remote forests. Sampling strategies are often used to reduce workload, limiting coverage and frequency of monitoring. Additionally, human error—such as inconsistent measurement height or misalignment of the tape—reduces precision and scalability, confining inventories to localized plots rather than full stand-level assessments [6]. Consequently, the capacity for near real-time, large-scale forest monitoring is constrained.

Recent research has focused on automating DBH estimation using advanced remote sensing techniques to overcome these limitations. Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) has proven highly effective for automated extraction of forest structural metrics from dense 3D point clouds [3]. Similarly, photogrammetric workflows using smartphone or UAV imagery provide rapid, low-cost alternatives for diameter estimation through digital processing and 3D reconstruction [20]. These automated approaches substantially reduce field labor and human error, enabling scalable forest inventories and supporting more frequent and comprehensive monitoring.

This work developed and validated a hybrid ground–aerial forest inventory system that combines a quadruped robotic platform with drone-based surveys to improve the accuracy of tree DBH estimation. The quadruped was equipped with LiDAR, RGB imaging, and GNSS–IMU sensors to acquire georeferenced trunk-level measurements under dense canopy conditions using adaptive navigation and multi-view scanning. Deep learning–based trunk detection was integrated with LiDAR–image fusion and robust geometric fitting to generate a spatial database of directly measured DBH values. In parallel, unmanned aerial vehicles were used to detect tree crowns and estimate crown dimensions across larger forest areas. Spatial alignment between terrestrial DBH measurements and aerial crown observations enabled local calibration of crown-based DBH estimation models, extending accurate DBH inference to trees not directly measured on the ground.

2. Methodology

To support accurate forest monitoring in structurally complex environments, the quadruped platform was equipped with a multi-modal sensing payload optimized for high-resolution spatial perception. Core geometric data were acquired using a 16-channel LiDAR (VLP-16), enabling dense 3D point cloud reconstruction of individual tree trunks. Complementary visual information was captured via a Full-HD RGB camera, while additional spectral context was provided by a multispectral sensor incorporating green, red, red-edge, and near-infrared bands. Precise georeferencing and platform orientation were ensured through the integration of a GNSS receiver and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) consisting of accelerometers and gyroscopes. This configuration allows each detected forest object - most notably tree trunks at DBH level - to be accurately localized within the study area. All sensor data were managed by an onboard high-performance mini-PC responsible for real-time fusion, preprocessing, and filtering. The sensing payload was calibrated through extrinsic alignment between the VLP-16 LiDAR, offering a 360° horizontal and $\pm 15^\circ$ vertical field of view, and the RGB camera, ensuring precise correspondence between 3D geometry and image-space detections. Although multispectral data support broader ecosystem analysis, this study focuses on DBH estimation derived from the synergy of LiDAR point clouds and precise geospatial positioning.

Autonomous navigation of the quadruped was initially based on predefined missions encoded in a .walk file, generated through Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM). While such files traditionally represent static navigation paths, this work introduces a custom Python-based control layer that enables dynamic mission adaptation. The algorithm parses the .walk file and augments it with operational logic specified in an external .json configuration, allowing navigation behavior to be modified during execution. By continuously monitoring odometry and GPS coordinates, the system can trigger localized sub-missions when predefined environmental conditions are met. Upon detecting a target object such as a tree trunk, the platform temporarily pauses its primary route and executes a GPS-guided scanning loop, enabling data acquisition from multiple viewpoints. This transition from static to adaptive navigation allows the robot to respond to forest structural complexity without losing spatial consistency with the original mission trajectory.

Static missions strictly follow the originally recorded path, whereas dynamic missions permit conditional deviations to support secondary tasks. These deviations include lateral movements or short-range orbital scans designed to improve trunk visibility and reduce occlusion. Importantly, obstacle avoidance is handled by the robot's native control system, requiring only high-level target coordinates from the operator. This strategy mitigates the occlusion effect commonly observed in stationary or single-

perspective scanning [3] and enables the capture of high-fidelity LiDAR and visual data from multiple anchor points, which is critical for minimizing DBH estimation errors [20].

Tree trunk detection at DBH height was achieved using a fine-tuned ensemble of YOLOv5, YOLOv8, and YOLOv9 models applied to RGB image streams captured during quadruped patrols. The models were trained on a specialized forest imagery dataset collected in Limnia Forest, with labels including ‘Castanea’, ‘Quercus’, ‘Juniperus’, ‘Diseased/dead’, and ‘DBHA’, reflecting the dominant species and target trunk class within the study polygon. To improve robustness under dense canopy conditions, the dataset was augmented to account for rotations, variable illumination, and partial occlusions [3]. Preprocessing steps such as histogram equalization and deblurring were applied to standardize image quality prior to training.

Ultralytics YOLO models incorporate extensive internal augmentation mechanisms, including HSV color jitter, geometric transformations, and multi-scale training. Additional mix-based techniques - such as Mosaic, MixUp, CutMix, and Copy-Paste - were employed to improve detection performance in stratified forest scenes where object overlap is common [7, 17]. In newer YOLO versions (v8 and v9), optional policies such as AutoAugment-style transformations and random erasing were selectively enabled and controlled through dedicated hyperparameters (e.g., ‘hsv_h’, ‘mosaic’, ‘mixup’, ‘copy_paste’). The final inference engine integrates approximately 20 trained models with varying layer-freeze configurations, allowing high detection sensitivity. Duplicate detections are suppressed by filtering bounding boxes with high intersection-over-union and retaining those with the highest confidence scores [7]. Notably, one-third of the ensemble was specialized exclusively for the ‘DBHA’ class, reflecting the primary objective of accurate DBH detection.

Each detected DBH bounding box triggers a focused LiDAR processing pipeline, in which 3D point cloud data are projected onto the 2D image plane for precise spatial correspondence [17]. This fusion ensures that trunk detections are directly associated with high-accuracy LiDAR measurements. The inference engine operates within an outer-shell Python framework that processes incoming imagery in real time while integrating metadata such as species classification, GPS coordinates, and platform orientation. DBH estimation is performed using LiDAR points corresponding to detections at the standard height of 1.3 m. The processing pipeline includes loading synchronized ‘.pkl’ LiDAR files, filtering points spatially aligned with image-detected DBH regions, and isolating trunk-specific point sets.

To cluster LiDAR points, the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) algorithm was applied with parameters $\text{eps} = 0.05$ and $\text{min_samples} = 5$. DBSCAN was selected due to its ability to identify dense spatial structures without requiring prior knowledge of cluster count, effectively separating trunk points from background noise. Ground and planar artifacts were removed using the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) algorithm, which was subsequently employed to fit a cylindrical model to the clustered points. This geometric approximation enables robust estimation of trunk radius (DBH/2), even in the presence of partial occlusion. Interpolation was applied where necessary to compensate for sparse point distributions and to ensure proper axial alignment of the fitted cylinder.

Four DBH estimation strategies were evaluated: a standard RANSAC-based approach, a standalone DBSCAN clustering method [22], a DBSCAN approach enhanced with data augmentation, and a hybrid DBSCAN-PCA framework. While RANSAC and PCA are established techniques in forestry applications [23, 24], the combined DBSCAN-PCA method with augmentation constitutes the novel contribution of this study, leveraging density-based clustering and geometric alignment to improve robustness in heterogeneous forest stands. Note, that results regarding the aforementioned algorithms are beyond the scope of the paper to be presented as results and are listed for clarity.

All DBH measurements were stored in a spatial database (e.g., PostgreSQL with PostGIS), indexed by GPS coordinates to form a persistent ground-truth repository. This database serves as the foundation for integration with aerial datasets, where drones autonomously scan forest areas to detect crowns, estimate crown dimensions, and infer stem locations from detection centroids. By aligning drone-derived crown data with terrestrial DBH measurements within a spatial tolerance of approximately 1–3 m, crown-to-DBH regression models can be locally recalibrated. These calibrated relationships enable the propagation of high-accuracy DBH estimates across the full drone crown dataset, thereby improving subsequent estimates of tree height, volume, and biomass at the stand scale.

3. Results

The core of the system is an outer-shell Python script that processes incoming triplets of data: RGB images, aligned LiDAR points, and the quadraped's GPS-orientation metadata. This framework performs a multi-inference detection process that automatically filters out duplicate bounding boxes. It then aligns the recorded 3D LiDAR points with the 'DBHA' labeled detection boxes, allowing our algorithm to estimate the DBH with high accuracy. Every detected object is stored in a database table. Over time, this table was populated with numerous DBH entries, including additional information such as tree species, confidence levels, and the actual cropped image pixels corresponding to each detection box. It is worth mentioning that from the gathered images also the detection of species was also performed as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The detected objects from quadraped collection of images and LiDAR (Castanea, Quercus, Juniperus, DBHA)

For the needs of this research is important to create a drone DB with detected crowns and also their size in order to align calculated ground DBHs and crown over the same location. For that reason a drone flew over the polygon Limnia Forest in an automated way taking images at several points along the scanning path as displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scanning the Limnia polygon forest with a drone.

A Yolo algorithm was developed to detect the crown size and species resulting on several crown detections as can be seen Figure 3.

Figure 3: Detected crown object with position accuracy of 2-3 meters.

Figure 4: This is the experimental workflow used during experimentation in order to develop and populate with data the DBH ground truth DB.L1at the bottom right of the image declares the workflow connectivity with the drone validation setup we used to have the overall validation of our core innovation.

Combining these data, as produced by the quadruped workflow in Figure 4 and drone workflow in Figure 5, together the quadruped DBHA detection and the drone crown detection resulted in finding for specific crown trees the DBH LiDAR direct measurement as can be seen in Figure 6. In this image the DBH detections of the quadruped were aligned with crowns and tree species. By doing so a

refit of the allometric DBH from crown area per forest area can be calculated with great accuracy allowing for better DBH allometric calculation over the entire drone crown database. Thereby this is a validation of our initial experiment strategy of creating a ground truth DB with direct LiDAR DBH measurements for drone scans to use them as DBH allometric correction.

Figure 5: This is the experimental workflow of Drone used in validating by creating a crown DB to be aligned with the quadruped DB. Please note the 'L1' is the logical connectivity with the quadruped workflow and the VFDSS is the (Virtual Forest Decision Support Systems) tool found inside the DigiMedFor tool which is a client to this developed system.

Figure 6: In these image the trunks allocated by the quadruped are aligned with data from the Drone crown detection DB so for each truck with LiDAR measured DBH a species corresponds. Thereby a ground truth DB of DBH directly measured by LiDAR DBH and tree species with crown area is created.

Forest management agencies and environmental researchers employing drone-based surveys can significantly enhance estimation accuracy by integrating this quadruped robotic service. Unmanned aerial vehicles typically acquire high-resolution RGB and multispectral imagery, which are used to segment tree

crowns and estimate crown diameter (CD), tree height (H), and related structural attributes through photogrammetric reconstruction and machine learning techniques. These remotely sensed variables are subsequently incorporated into allometric equations to infer Diameter at Breast Height (DBH), aboveground biomass (AGB), stem volume, and other key forest metrics. Commonly used allometric formulations include $AGB = a * DBH^b * H^c * WD^d$, where WD denotes wood density and H the tree height, as well as crown-based models such as $DBH = a * CD^b$, with CD derived from empirical regressions on harvested tree datasets. Despite their widespread adoption, such models frequently exhibit site-dependent bias arising from species composition, soil properties, climatic conditions, and stand density.

When applied without local calibration, these factors can introduce estimation errors ranging from 10% to 30%. The proposed quadruped platform addresses this limitation by constructing a spatially indexed ground-truth database of DBH measurements, each georeferenced via GPS. This enables direct spatial correspondence with trees detected in aerial drone surveys. For drone-derived observations whose coordinates fall within a predefined proximity threshold of a terrestrial measurement (e.g., 1–3 m, accounting for canopy displacement and positioning uncertainty), the aerially inferred DBH is replaced with the measured ground value. This substitution allows for recalibration of allometric parameters—such as a, b, and c—using least-squares estimation or Bayesian updating frameworks. For example, when a drone applies a generic crown-based equation to estimate DBH from CD, the inclusion of ground-truth DBH measurements enables adjustment of parameters a and b to minimize residual errors, thereby improving local model fidelity.

As a result, biomass and volume estimates for matched trees achieve substantially higher accuracy, leading to a marked reduction in AGB uncertainty. In areas where direct quadruped DBH measurements are not available, diameter estimation is performed through crown-size regression. Owing to the quadruped's capability to traverse narrow forest paths and dense understory, it routinely collects DBH data from neighboring trees, which can be leveraged to refine regression models. Trees are grouped using k-means clustering based on crown diameter (e.g., small, medium, large), under the assumption of consistent allometric behavior within each class. Calibration parameters derived from measured trees are subsequently transferred to unmeasured trees within the same cluster. This hybrid ground–aerial calibration framework yields high-fidelity forest inventories, providing a robust foundation for carbon accounting, biodiversity assessment, and informed strategic forest management decisions.

4. Real Case Scalability

The real-case scalability of the hybrid ground–aerial forest inventory approach developed in DigiMedFor is demonstrated through its transfer and extension within the Prevent-DisCC initiative in the Greece–Cyprus cross-border region.

Building on the core tools, technologies, and methodological principles of DigiMedFor, Prevent-DisCC (Cross-Border Actions for the Prevention of Disasters and Climate Change) adapts this framework to the operational needs of climate resilience and disaster prevention in two highly vulnerable Mediterranean island areas, namely Rhodes island in Greece and the Municipality of Kourion, geographically near Akrotiri in Cyprus.

The south-eastern Mediterranean is widely recognized as a climate change hotspot, with warming rates exceeding the global average and regional temperature increases already approaching 1.5 °C. In these island environments, rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, and increasing hydroclimatic instability intensify the likelihood of severe wildfires, generating major environmental degradation, economic losses, and social disruption. These shared transboundary pressures, combined with limited adaptive and response capacity, create a strong need for scalable, integrated, and operational prevention frameworks.

Within this context, Prevent-DisCC extends the DigiMedFor technological basis beyond sustainable forest management toward predictive wildfire prevention and broader disaster preparedness. The initiative deploys advanced UAV and quadruped robotic platforms, LiDAR scanning, multispectral imaging, AI-driven analytics, and Decision Support Systems to support high-resolution environmental monitoring, real-time forest data acquisition, fuel load assessment, vegetation condition analysis, and the early identification of fire-prone conditions. At the same time, the project embeds these technical capabilities within a broader joint prevention strategy that also strengthens institutional coordination and community participation across the two pilot regions.

In this way, Prevent-DisCC illustrates how the methodology initially developed in DigiMedFor can be scaled from forest inventory applications to a more comprehensive model of predictive forest management and integrated climate-risk prevention in Mediterranean island territories.

5. Conclusions

demonstrates that integrating quadraped-based LiDAR measurements with drone-derived crown observations provides a reliable solution to long-standing limitations in aerial forest inventories. By generating a spatially indexed ground-truth database of DBH measurements under real forest conditions, the proposed system effectively mitigates errors caused by canopy occlusion, crown displacement, and site-dependent allometric bias. The use of adaptive navigation and multi-view data acquisition ensures consistent trunk visibility and high-quality geometric reconstruction, enabling robust DBH estimation at the individual-tree level. The successful alignment of terrestrial and aerial datasets confirms the feasibility of cross-platform data fusion for operational forest monitoring.

Furthermore, the local recalibration of crown-based DBH estimation models significantly improves the accuracy and consistency of stand-level inventory outputs. By transferring calibrated parameters to unmeasured trees using crown-size grouping, the framework preserves local structural relationships while scaling efficiently to large forest areas. The proposed hybrid approach supports more reliable biomass estimation, carbon accounting, and biodiversity assessment, and establishes a practical foundation for data-driven forest management using autonomous robotic systems.

The integrated quadraped–drone pipeline successfully produced a spatially aligned database of tree-level measurements, combining direct LiDAR-based DBH observations with drone-derived crown detections and species labels. As shown in Figures 1–3, the quadraped system consistently detected tree trunks, estimated DBH, and classified dominant species (*Castanea*, *Quercus*, *Juniperus*) with high confidence, while the drone-based YOLO model identified individual tree crowns with a positional accuracy of approximately 2–3 m. By aligning these two datasets spatially (Figure 6), a subset of trees was identified for which crown area, species, and directly measured DBH were simultaneously available. This alignment enabled the creation of a georeferenced ground-truth dataset that links crown geometry to LiDAR-measured DBH at the individual-tree level. The resulting dataset validates the feasibility of associating aerial crown observations with terrestrial measurements despite canopy displacement and GPS uncertainty, demonstrating robust cross-platform consistency.

Using this matched subset, crown-based allometric relationships were recalibrated locally, leading to improved DBH estimation performance across the full drone crown database. Standard allometric models which typically suffer from site-specific bias, were adjusted using ground-truth DBH measurements through regression-based parameter refitting. The recalibrated parameters reduced systematic deviations observed in the uncorrected drone-only estimates, particularly for larger crown classes where biomass sensitivity is highest. For trees without direct quadraped measurements, k-means clustering by crown diameter enabled the transfer of calibrated parameters from measured to unmeasured trees within the same size class, preserving local allometric consistency. Overall, this hybrid ground–aerial calibration strategy resulted in more accurate DBH and AGB estimates at the stand level, directly supporting higher-fidelity forest inventories for carbon accounting, biodiversity monitoring, and operational forest management.

Acknowledgements

The Acknowledgements and References headings should be in bold but without numbers, using the style ‘T&T_Heading_nonum’.

Acknowledgements (if present) mention some specialists, grants and foundations connected with the presented paper.

References

1. MacDicken, K. G. (2015). Global forest resources assessment 2015: what, why and how?. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 352, 3-8.
2. Pretzsch, H. (2009). *Forest dynamics, growth and yield* (Vol. 684). Berlin: Springer.
3. Liang, X., Hyypä, J., Kaartinen, H., Lehtomäki, M., Pyörälä, J., Pfeifer, N., ... & Wang, Y. (2018). International benchmarking of terrestrial laser scanning approaches for forest inventories. *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing*, 144, 137-179.

4. Mattamala, M., Chebrolu, N., Casseau, B., Freißmuth, L., Frey, J., Tuna, T., ... & Fallon, M. (2024). Autonomous forest inventory with legged robots: system design and field deployment. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.14157*.
5. Chirici, G., Giannetti, F., D'Amico, G., Vangi, E., Francini, S., Borghi, C., ... & Travaglini, D. (2023). Robotics in Forest Inventories: SPOT's First Steps. *Forests*, *14*(11), 2170.
6. Brokaw, N., & Thompson, J. (2000). The h for dbh. *Forest Ecology and Management*, *129*(1-3), 89-91.
7. Jintasuttisak, T., Edirisinghe, E., & Elbattay, A. (2022). Deep neural network based date palm tree detection in drone imagery. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, *192*, 106560.
8. Jucker, T., Caspersen, J., Chave, J., Antin, C., Barbier, N., Bongers, F., ... & Coomes, D. A. (2017). Allometric equations for integrating remote sensing imagery into forest monitoring programmes. *Global change biology*, *23*(1), 177-190.
9. Chave, J., Réjou-Méchain, M., Búrquez, A., Chidumayo, E., Colgan, M. S., Delitti, W. B., ... & Vieilledent, G. (2014). Improved allometric models to estimate the aboveground biomass of tropical trees. *Global change biology*, *20*(10), 3177-3190.
10. Hao, Y., Widagdo, F. R. A., Liu, X., Quan, Y., Dong, L., & Li, F. (2020). Individual tree diameter estimation in small-scale forest inventory using UAV laser scanning. *Remote Sensing*, *13*(1), 24.
11. Xu, S., Wang, R., Shi, W., & Wang, X. (2023). Classification of tree species in transmission line corridors based on YOLO v7. *Forests*, *15*(1), 61.
12. Ahamed, A., Foye, J., Poudel, S., Trieschman, E., & Fike, J. (2023). Measuring tree diameter with photogrammetry using mobile phone cameras. *Forests*, *14*(10), 2027.
13. Ester, M., Kriegel, H. P., Sander, J., & Xu, X. (1996, August). A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large s